

Short assignment No 2 for BME 08

Student name: Michail Fragkos

Abstract

1. Introduction

During Professor Konstantinidis's lecture in the Module 8 of the Biomedical Engineering (BME) MSc program of Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH) about Persistent Identifiable Data (PID) and Open Science, the students were tasked with creating a number of PIDs themselves and use them in an analysis as part of the Research Analysis Identifier System (RAISE), in order to better understand their purpose and usability. PIDs are a way of persistently describing a variety of objects, namely scientific articles, datasets, software, experiments or even organizations (scholar institutions) and people (researchers) ^[1]. The most important and frequent of the PIDs is the Digital Object Identifier (DOI), which uses a specific form of nomenclature to identify an object of the aforementioned kinds and is widely used in a great number of scientific fields. The final purpose of this assignment was to search the name of a researcher of the students' choice in OpenAlex, a graph that connects scholarly objects by their PIDs, and run an experiment about their publications with a script provided by the professor ^[3].

2. Methods

During this assignment, the author's Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID) was used to claim authorship of any created object and it was furtherly linked with newly created accounts in Zenodo, an open-access data repository using PIDs for identification, and in the RAISE portal, a place for running analyses and experiments and directly generating PIDs for them. Afterwards, OpenAlex was used, and a researcher, Professor Asimina Galli was searched for an analysis of her publications. The reason behind the choice of this researcher is the author's interest in pediatrics and pediatric endocrinology, as prof. Galli, a professor doctor specializing in pediatric endocrinology, is one of the most acknowledged and cited researchers in this field in Greece and worldwide. Continuing, information collected from OpenAlex, in the form of a Comma Separated Values (CSV) file, was used in the RAISE portal in an experiment together with a script by Prof. Konstantinidis^[3], providing an analysis of this information in the form of text and more importantly, images and graphs, as for example in Figure 1.

3. Results

The experiment analysis created graphs connecting the researcher, prof. Galli with her most frequent co-authors in a form of a network, providing a clear visualization of the authors connections (See Figure 1). Moreover, an analysis of the type of publications (open access vs closed access) was conducted to provide an overview of the researcher's preferences and trends in this field and additionally number of citations was compared in these 2 types, to find any similarities or differences.

4. Discussion

Firstly, as for the results of the experiment, one can easily visualize the professor's preference to some of her collaborators in the form of bigger circles and arrows (see Figure 1.) and observe what the trends in open access compared to closed access are. Moreover, based on the whole procedure of this assignment, one can clearly witness the importance of PIDs as part of the FAIR principles for scientific data management [2]. Data should be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) and that is exactly what is achieved via the PIDs.

Figure 1. Co-Authorship Network Analysis for Prof. Galli

5. Conclusions

This assignment underlines the importance of PIDs and helps with understanding the various uses of them in science. All objects created during this assignment are published and linked with their corresponding DOI (see Table 1.).

Author's ORCID:	https://orcid.org/0009-0005-2945-7949
Researcher's (Prof. Galli) ORCID:	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8503-3893
PID of used dataset:	https://doi.org/10.82136/dataset/08de8ffb-a802-4e40-803b-d79f2cef376e
PIDs of used script:	https://doi.org/10.82136/script/08de790c-58a3-47dc-8475-cc889e4fe833 (in RAISE), https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19654960 (in Zenodo)
PID of experiment:	https://doi.org/10.82136/371
PID of assignment:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19700178

Table 1. PIDs used in the course of the present assignment

6. References

1. Nason, M. (2024, July 6). Getting found, staying found: Persistent identifiers (PIDs) and their value. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10850033>
2. Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, Ij. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.-W., da Silva Santos, L. B., Bourne, P. E., Bouwman, J., Brookes, A. J., Clark, T., Crosas, M., Dillo, I., Dumon, O., Edmunds, S., Evelo, C. T., Finkers, R., ... Mons, B. (2016). The Fair Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
3. Konstantinidis, E. (2026b, March 3). Openalex researcher work analysis v_5. RAISE Portal. <https://doi.org/10.82136/script/08de790c-58a3-47dc-8475-cc889e4fe833>